

STATIC PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF FAUST PROGRAMS USING DATAFLOW MODELLING

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ABSTRACT

The processing capabilities of modern System-on-Chips allow artists to push the boundaries of digital art by enabling the implementation of complex real-time signal processing applications. The Faust framework has simplified the process of implementing signal processing applications for these systems. With the Faust language, it is possible to generate implementations for a wide variety of target contexts, allowing users to take a “write once, implement everywhere” approach. Nonetheless, this variety of hardware also comes with the issue of determining what kind of processing capability is required for a given project.

Evaluation tools of Faust currently rely on runtime analysis to measure the performance of implementations on target hardware; this method can be time consuming and requires the user to already own the hardware they wish to evaluate.

Instead, we attempt to address this problem by considering static performance analysis. We propose to use a dataflow model of computation to represent Faust programs, and to predict performance for specific target hardware. This approach could provide useful heuristics in the future for users to decide which hardware is needed to reach their required performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Computers and Embedded systems are a significant enabler of audiovisual digital art [1]. In the early 90s, artists started to use increasingly affordable System-on-Chip (SoC) [2]. Nowadays, a variety of systems are available across a range of performance capabilities and price points; they often contain highly efficient devices such as Graphic Processing Units (GPUs), Digital Signal Processors, and Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) that pave the way for new generations of digital art movements [3]. It is therefore becoming increasingly viable for artists who wish to take advantage of specialised processor capabilities to purchase these systems.

Nonetheless, programming these modern systems can be tedious, often requiring some level of engineering expertise, resulting in high barriers to entry.

The Faust programming language addresses this problem by providing a Domain Specific Language (DSL) for audio signal processing, and a compiler framework that can be used to generate programs in a wide variety of languages compatible with various hardware architectures. Users can therefore take a “write once, implement everywhere” approach for the targets that the Faust compiler supports.

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Figure 1: Overview of workflow with/without SDF modelling

While programming these systems has been simplified, the variety of devices available and across a range of costs led us toward the following questions:

- What hardware is needed for a particular (Faust) program?
- Could the (Faust) programming framework point the user towards the minimal required target?

Performance metrics exist to indicate whether a system performs well or not. In the case of audio processing, to match the sampling rate of the system, it is necessary to process samples at a rate of at least 44.1kHz — this is known as the throughput of the system. Additionally, the time taken for the system to produce output samples from input samples also matters — this is known as the system’s latency. In practice, the time taken to process a sample needs to remain within 10% of the fraction of time that the sample represents. Furthermore, the latency of an audio processing system is largely influenced by the buffer size used. Factors surrounding a system’s implementation of audio processing, such as its audio card, analogue-to-digital/digital-to-analog converters, and communications protocol, can also impact its overall latency. In the context of digital musical instruments, the acceptable upper bound for latency is expected to lie between 10ms to 30ms [4, 5, 6]; exceeding that bound would make it increasingly likely for a user to detect this latency and degrade their performance with the instrument.

Faust includes benchmarking tools to measure the throughput of a given Faust program, however, its primary purpose is to evaluate the performance of different compilation schemes used by the Faust compiler [7, 8]. While this provides insight into the overall performance of the given Faust program, the measured results are dependant on the hardware that the benchmark tools are run on. Evaluating the performance of the same program on different hardware and for different configurations would therefore require additional testing with implementations on the corresponding target hardware. There are shortcomings to this approach. Firstly, re-implementing and running benchmark tests on multiple target hardware can be time consuming. Moreover, this form of testing requires the user to already own the hardware they intend to test their program on; resulting in unnecessary effort and expenditure should the program prove to be unsuitable for the given hardware.

Instead, we propose to rely on static analysis to estimate the performance of a program. Our objective is to divorce performance evaluation from actually running the Faust program on the target hardware.

In the case of general purpose languages (e.g. C or Java) and modern processors (out-of-order CPU with memory caches), due to their high complexity, instrumentation and simulation are preferred to static analysis. However, previous works have shown that when either of these conditions are relaxed by using more deterministic hardware, or simply reducing the expressiveness of the programming language, successful performance estimation can be reached [9].

Fortunately, as a domain specific language, the Faust language has a reduced expressivity and thus has the potential to be successfully used in the context of static performance analysis. For example, there are similarities between the Faust programming language and dataflow models of computation such as Synchronous dataflow graphs [10] (SDFGs).

These models are commonly used in the context of digital signal processing (DSP), describing applications as a set of actors communicating via First-in-First-out (FIFO) buffers. Execution times and communication rates between actors are fixed — this strongly facilitates static analysis, including performance prediction. Numerous frameworks have been proposed that effectively predict the correctness and performance of SDF programs [11, 12].

The decision not to use a dataflow model in Faust’s design has been discussed by Orlarey et al. [13] — the complexity and overheads involved in implementing a dataflow model were highlighted as its key shortcomings. Nonetheless, there are benefits to using a dataflow representation as a model for program analysis rather than a runtime model.

Once we model a Faust program as an SDFG, by reusing these existing frameworks, we could anticipate the performance of Faust programs on various hardware without having to actually implement the program on the target hardware, thereby avoiding the shortcomings of the current benchmarking methodology. This approach also allows the performance of Faust programs to be statically evaluated as SDFGs, providing the user with information that may help with optimizing their programs.

In service of this goal, we made the following contributions:

- Describe a model transformation from Faust to SDFG,
- Implemented a compilation scheme that performs this transformation,
- Demonstrate its advantages using several use cases.

We start in Section 2 by providing an overview of Faust and the methods currently available for benchmarking programs. We then present the nomenclature of the dataflow model of computation and, accordingly, how Faust programs can be expressed as an SDF graph in Section 3. As mentioned before, there are benefits to be gained from utilising an SDF model of Faust programs in the process of generating target implementations. In Section 4, we explain the various performance analysis results that are obtainable from SDFGs and show how this model could aid the developer in determining which implementation is most suitable for their given program. We also speculate on potential future applications of the SDF model in the context of implementing Faust programs. Naturally, our proposed use of SDF modelling is not without its shortcomings; the limitations of this approach as well as the potential challenges that might be faced in developing this approach are highlighted in Section 5.

2. THE FAUST LANGUAGE

Faust is a programming language meant to facilitate the implementation of real-time audio signal processing and audio synthesis programs. It is a functional programming language consisting of a signal processing semantic for describing block diagram algebra [13]. It is one of several languages for computer music; these are programming languages that tend to prioritize aspects such as timing, concurrency, and collaboration to facilitate audio synthesis and musical composition [14]. In contrast to most other computer music languages, however, the Faust programming language centres around mathematically expressing signal flow and operations.

2.1. Syntax

As we will be presenting some basic examples of Faust programs in this paper, we provide a brief overview of the language in order to familiarize the reader with the necessary subset of its syntax and semantics. We encourage readers to look to Orlarey *et al.*’s paper for a formal specification of the syntax and semantics of the Faust language [13].

2.1.1. Signals

A signal consists of a stream of sample values that are produced at a fixed sampling rate (e.g. 48000Hz). As the Faust language is primarily concerned with describing digital signal processors, it typically takes in signals as inputs (“input signals”), and produces signals as outputs (“output signals”). The input signals tend to be audio signals, such as those produced by a microphone or an audio file.

2.1.2. Primitives

The Faust language includes several primitives that operate on signals. For the purpose of this paper, we list only three types of primitives:

- Arithmetic primitives (+, −, *, /, %)
- Fixed delay (@)
- Identity primitive (⊆)

Arithmetic primitives consist of five operators — +, −, *, /, % — which correspond to the addition, subtraction, product, division, and modulo operators respectively. Fixed delay, denoted by ‘@’,

is used to denote an n sample delay between the arrival of an input signal and the production of its output signal. Finally, the identity primitive, denoted by ‘ $_$ ’, simply refers to the identity function for its input signal.

2.1.3. Composition Operations

To describe the flow of signals between Faust primitives, Faust uses five binary composition operators. We list two of these for the purposes of the examples used in this paper.

- Sequential ($;$)
- Parallel ($,$)

By composing signals with primitives, the Faust language can be used to describe signal processing programs. We demonstrate this with an example Faust program:

```
process = _, 2 : / : _, 1 : +;
```

Listing 1: A simple Faust program

The program described in Listing 1 can be broken up into a four-step sequence ($s_1:s_2:s_3:s_4$). The first step is a parallel composition of the input signal (as identity $_$) and the numerical value 2. The second step applies the division operator to the parallel signals, thus dividing the input signal by 2. The third step is again a parallel composition consisting of the output of the division operator (as identity $_$) and the numerical value 1. Lastly, the addition operator is applied to the parallel signals. Mathematically, if we denote i the input sample, then this simple program computes $(i/2) + 1$ for each i to compute the corresponding output signal.

Arithmetic primitives and composition operators, along with those not introduced in this section, are thus used to describe signal processing programs. The Faust compiler then compiles the given Faust program to the specified target implementation. Faust provides a benchmark tool to evaluate the performance of the compiled program — the details of which will be covered in Section 2.2.

2.2. Benchmark Tools

Faust provides an ALSA GTK application (CoreAudio for OSX) that can be used to measure the throughput of the given Faust program in terms of megabytes of samples that the program can process per second (MB/s) [8]. This is done by taking a fixed number of timing measurements, converted from processor cycles, which are subsequently used to compute the MB/s achieved by the program. This throughput performance indicator can be used to estimate an upper bound on the speed of a program [7].

Faust includes a suite of benchmark test programs in its distribution — this was initially used to measure the performance impacts of two compilation schemes that added various forms of parallelisations to Faust programs [7]. Subsequently, additional benchmark tools were implemented to evaluate the performance of WebAssembly code generated from Faust programs [15].

While the benchmarking tools can be used to estimate the performance of a given Faust program [7], the results gained are dependent on the characteristics of the machine it is run on. Related to this, the average of several measurements have to be taken as well in order to ensure that the results are stable.¹ The entire

¹As mentioned in the readme of the Faust benchmark tool: <https://github.com/grame-cncm/faust/tree/master-dev/benchmark>.

benchmarking process can therefore be a time-consuming and subjective process.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this section, we first introduce our methodology, then we recall the SDF model that will be used to represent Faust programs. Following which, we explain how signal graphs generated by the Faust compiler are transformed into equivalent SDF representations.

3.1. Overview

3.1.1. Existing Workflow

Figure 1 illustrates an overview of the workflow of writing, generating, and evaluating the performance of a program with Faust. The black portions of the chart indicate the workflow given the current set of benchmarking tools. After writing a program in Faust, users would then compile the program by specifying a target architecture to obtain a program suitable for this target. To evaluate the performance of their code, they would have to run their program using the benchmark tool to obtain the latency and/or throughput of the program executed on the given hardware.

If the compiled implementation does not meet their constraints, they would then have to modify the Faust program before restarting the process — this is indicated in Figure 1 by the black edge from “Benchmark results” to “Faust program”. Ultimately, if these modifications were not deemed to be sufficient, the user would need to target a different hardware, and repeat the process.

3.1.2. Our Approach

The blue components in Figure 1 indicate the modified workflow from utilising an SDF model of the Faust program. Prior to compiling the Faust program for a given implementation, it is first modelled as an SDF graph, as indicated by the edge labelled “Generate SDF model” in Figure 1. We would then be able to take advantage of static analysis techniques for SDF graphs to predict its performance prior to running the program. Shortcomings in performance could be identified and corrected at this stage; this is indicated by the feedback loop on the “SDF model” component. On top of avoiding the repeated steps of implementation and running the benchmarking tools, these performance evaluation could be performed for several kind of hardware, helping to identify which device would be the best fit for any particular application.

For example, instead of measuring the latency or the throughput of a particular Faust program at run-time, we could utilise latency and throughput computation techniques designed for SDF graphs. These would allow us to predict the performance of a Faust program without having to implement it on the target machine. Furthermore, we would not experience the same variability as in benchmarking results. In the following sections, we introduce the SDF model followed by our transformation methodology.

3.2. Data-Driven Models

The dataflow computational model represents programs as directed graphs. The nodes of the graph are actors that represent operations to be executed on input data to produce output data. The edges connecting these nodes are channels, which represent first in, first out (FIFO) buffers through which tokens of data (“tokens”,

Figure 2: Example of a Synchronous Dataflow Graph.

in short) flow between actors [16]. These channels can be specified with an initial number of tokens (“initial tokens”) in their FIFO buffers before the beginning of actor executions. In the context of signal processing programs, a single token would refer to a single sample of a signal. In this model, actors can only be executed when the required number of tokens are available on their input channels, thereby allowing multiple actors to execute in parallel without relying on a centralized control mechanism. In this manner, the dataflow model is a data-driven model, where valid executions of an actor are determined by the availability of the prerequisite data on its input edges.

Synchronous Dataflow (SDF) [10] is a subset of the dataflow computational model. The distinguishing feature of SDF is that the data production and consumption rates of each actor are constant and statically defined [10]. Figure 2 illustrates an example of a simple SDF graph made up of 4 actors. The production and consumption rates are denoted by the numbers in square brackets above the edges going out and into the actor. Actor C, for example, consumes 4 tokens produced by A and 6 tokens produced by B in order to produce 1 token onto the channel connecting C to D. The boxes lying on the edges denote the FIFO buffers through which the tokens flow between actors, while the numbers in the solid edged rectangles refer to the number of initial tokens in the corresponding buffers. Actor C, for example, can execute prior to the first executions of A and B as it already has the sufficient number of initial tokens on its incoming channels. Actor D, on the other hand, will not be able to execute until C executes at least once as it only has 1 initial token in its input channel when it requires 2 tokens to execute. We can thus see how the edges between actors model data dependencies.

An advantage of the SDF model is that, with statically defined production and consumption rates, it is possible to compute a valid execution schedule for the modelled application. This allows us to statically determine several properties of programs modelled using the SDF model:

- Will the program deadlock?
- Is it able to infinitely execute its actors while storing a bounded amount of data?
- How frequently can actors execute?

These analyses would not be possible with general dataflow models [17]. SDF is therefore commonly used to describe DSP applications (e.g. LTE encoders [18], Deep Neural Networks [19]) or to express parallelism for implementation on specialized hardware (e.g. GPU [20], FPGA [21]). By modelling Faust programs using the SDF model, we can apply the same static analysis techniques on signal processors described with the Faust language.

Figure 3: Signal expression generated from Listing 1

Figure 4: SDFG representation of the signal expression from Figure 3

3.3. Model Transformation

As mentioned in Section 2, Faust programs are written in a high-level functional style which can then be compiled to a variety of target languages and platforms. Part of the process of compiling Faust programs involves converting high-level block-diagram descriptions into equivalent signal expressions, which consist of nodes that consume and produce input and output signals along edges that denote the flow of signals between nodes.

The signal expression in Figure 3, for example, shows how an input signal is multiplied by a constant signal of value 0.5 and subsequently incremented by a constant signal of value 1 in order to produce the output signal. These signal expressions form the basis of generating the SDF model of the corresponding Faust program. We start by describing the ideal scenario in which a signal expression can be directly translated into an equivalent SDF representation before listing out the various modifications that need to be made for signal expression components that do not directly fit into the SDF model.

3.3.1. Generating Actors and Channels

The process of generating an SDF representation of a Faust program starts with generating a signal expression using the Faust compiler. It is worth noting that signal expressions closely resemble SDF graphs. In particular, they resemble a special type of SDF where the production and consumption rates of all actors are equal to 1 — these are known as Homogeneous Synchronous Dataflow graphs (HSDFG).

Looking at the signal expression in Figure 3, each node either provides a constant signal value for the operator it is connected to (such as ‘0.5’ or ‘1’), or represents an operation to be executed on its input data (such as ‘*’ and ‘+’). Given that operations act on a single sample per execution, they are modelled with a fixed consumption and production rate of 1 unit of data per execution. Each operator and each constant are thus modelled as HSDF actors with channels interconnecting them in the same manner that they are connected in the signal expression.

Figure 5: Signal expression of *one-pole filter*

An exception to this are the ‘INPUT’ and ‘OUTPUT’ nodes, which represent the source and destination of the input and resulting output signal, respectively. For simplicity, we keep the production and consumption rates of these nodes at 1. However, these values can be changed to reflect different sampling rates, for example. We also model these nodes as actors.

By following these steps, the signal expression in Figure 3 can be modelled as the SDFG shown in Figure 4.

Unfortunately, signal expressions do not always map onto the SDF model as neatly as they do in the above example. In the remainder of this section, we describe the additional modifications involved in adapting signal expressions to the SDF model.

3.3.2. Modelling Delay in SDF

Operators in the signal expressions generated by Faust are not necessarily directly compatible with the SDF model; the delay operator is one such operator that we had to adapt to fit the SDF model. Figure 5 illustrates the signal expression of a one-pole filter implemented in Faust. As we can see, there is a cycle of nodes passing through $*$, $+$, REC_W0 , $Proj0$, and $@$. An equivalent SDF would deadlock, as each node would require the previous one to be executed. In such a case, initial values must be found in one of the cycle’s buffers to avoid any deadlock.

The $@$ node denotes a fixed delay operator. As mentioned in Section 2, the fixed delay operator is one of the Faust primitives. In a signal expression, it typically consists of an input signal and a node representing a constant integer signal denoting the delay length — a simplified version of the delay operator is illustrated in Figure 6. The delay operators in Figure 5 therefore delay sending the result of the addition operator to their respective output channels by 0 and 1 sample respectively. For this reason, in the first iteration, the product operator ($*$) will take 0 as an input sample.

Within SDF, initial values are also commonly known as “delay”, and perform similarly to delay operators of Faust. We thus replaced delay operators with channels initialized with n initial tokens of data of value 0, as shown in Figure 7. This is performed for each delay operator in order to model its behaviour in the resulting SDF graph. One caveat of this solution is when the delays within Faust programs are interactively controlled by the user with UI components, this case will be discussed in Section 5.

3.3.3. Timing Constraints

To perform any kind of timing analysis on SDFG, we need to determine the execution time for each actor as well as their resource constraints limiting their execution or communication patterns. These timings are related to the targeted architectures, and will change depending on the device.

Figure 6: Signal expression with delay of n samples

Figure 7: SDF-equivalent modelling delay function

For example, in the context of FPGAs hardware, tools such as the FloPoCo framework have shown that it is possible to automate arithmetic operator implementations with fixed timing guarantees at various frequencies [22].

In different hardware, where fixed guarantees are not achievable, it is sufficient to set the execution time of each actor according to their respective operator’s worst-case execution time (WCET). The execution times of the actors are thus set to any duration required by the operator to return a result after receiving its required input data.

However, due to memory accesses and the effect of caches, in devices such as CPUs, the communication time between actors can be much more important than the execution time of individual actors. In this context, rigorous hardware architecture models must be considered during the performance analysis [23].

4. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Modelling Faust programs as equivalent SDF representations allows us to apply the static analysis techniques available to SDFGs to programs implemented in Faust. In this section, we present two performance analysis use cases from modelling Faust programs as SDFGs: throughput, and delay. We provide examples of how these performance metrics can be used in the context of a Faust program that implements an echo effect on an input signal. The signal expression of this program, eponymously named *Echo*, is shown in Figure 8. Using the methodology explained in Section 3.3, we generated an SDF from the signal expression of *Echo*. In the process of doing so, we found that one of the delay primitives in Figure 8 had an argument that was determined by the value of a “hslider” component — the value of the signals from this component are controlled by the user at run-time. In order to express *Echo* as an SDF, we treated the “hslider” component, as well as the components it affected, as a constant value — the components of the signal expression involved in this are coloured grey in Figure 8.

The remaining components, which are coloured red, were then modelled as an SDF as shown in Figure 9. Using the method of modelling delay explained in Section 3.3.2, the argument provided to the delay primitive is denoted by the “ N ” initial tokens in the buffer between actor 1 and 4. Assuming a sampling rate (the value produced by ‘fSamplingFreq’ in Figure 8) of 48kHz, and observing that the “hslider” component has a range of 0.0 to 1000.0 with

a step size of 0.1, we found that “N” could take on values within the range of 0 to 47999.

4.1. Throughput

The throughput of an SDF is a measure of the rate at which it is able to process data — naturally, as actors consume and produce data, throughput is associated with the rate of actor execution in an SDFG. The period of an SDFG is the reciprocal of its throughput. It provides a measure of time elapsed between executions. There are several approaches to compute the throughput of an SDF [24]; one of which is to construct a schedule, which refers to an ordered sequence of actor firings. In particular, constructing a self-timed schedule, in which actors fire as soon as the required amount of data are available on each of their input channels, is one method to compute the maximum throughput of an SDF [25]. Once a periodic pattern of actor firings is established, the throughput can be computed as the average rate at which actors are fired in this pattern.

Naturally, existing throughput computation techniques assume that the SDFG accurately models the targeted hardware. For example, in the context of FPGA devices, where we can guarantee execution time in clock cycles for each arithmetic operator, Figure 10 shows the result of a self-timed schedule of Echo with a delay of $N = 3$ samples. It has a period of 14 cycles and, assuming a clock frequency of 400MHz, we can thus infer that the SDF in Figure 9 is able to operate at a frequency of approximately 28.5MHz; which is well above the required sampling rate of 48kHz.

4.2. Latency

Latency refers to the time difference between the arrival of a unit of data and the production of the corresponding output data [26]. Computing the latency of the SDFG is to determine the maximum time taken between an input sample and an output sample produced by the program. This can help the developer to determine if the latency of their current implementation meets their requirements. Furthermore, the process provides them with the actors whose execution times contribute to the latency of the program — reducing the execution times of these actors would therefore allow them to reduce the latency of their program.

For example from the Figure 10, we can see that there is a 20 cycle latency between the first execution of the input actor, and the first execution of the output actor, this is known as the First-to-First latency [27]. As noted in Section 1, the latency of an audio processing system is determined by factors beyond the time taken to compute a single sample. Nonetheless, this metric would be useful in guiding users towards selecting an appropriate buffer size.

5. LIMITATIONS

In this section, we discuss what we see as key limitations of our proposed approach and, where possible, suggest solutions to overcoming these limitations.

5.1. Timing Accuracy

In order to model a Faust program as an SDF, the execution times of each operator needs to be defined. However, these execution times are dependent on operation implementation which is, in turn, influenced by the hardware that it is being run on. Furthermore,

operator implementations do not always have guaranteed execution times; execution times can be affected by caching effects, for example. In cases such as this, it is necessary to define operator execution times as the WCET of the given operator implementation. For example, there has been prior work in implementing schedulers for SDFGs that take into account cache architectures in embedded DSP and uniprocessor architectures that might address this issue [28, 23]. This can lead to a considerable amount of effort to accurately compute the execution times to be used in the SDF. Furthermore, the variance of the execution times of operators could impact the accuracy of the performance analysis results.

5.2. Dynamic Variables

Faust programs can include components that users can interact with at run-time to change the values of variables. If these components are used to define the length of a delay operator, it would require the buffer used to model the delay operator to have a dynamic buffer size, thereby making the program incompatible with the SDF model. While we did present a workaround for the purpose of static performance analysis in Section 4.1, it should be noted that this could incur high costs in modelling programs with dynamic buffer sizes. The workaround presented in Section 4.1, for example, would require up to 48000 different versions of SDFGs to fully represent the different states of the system. That said, there are other potential solutions.

Scenario-Aware dataflow graphs [29], which are a parametric extension of SDF that can describe multiple modes of execution for the same application, is one potential solution. This could form the topic of a future work that aims to tackle the issues with expressing dynamic variables from Faust within the dataflow model.

5.3. Full-System Analysis

The analysis performed in previous SDFG examples, such as the maximum throughput or the latency analysis, do not consider the entire system targeted, but solely the compute part of it. In addition, there are multiple layers of communication and processing between the audio input interfaces and output ones, that are not considered and limit the performance of the overall system. Nonetheless, these analysis results can ensure by how much the compute part of this application will limit the overall system.

6. RELATED WORK

Our work look into the potential benefits of dataflow modelling to perform static performance analysis on DSP programs written in Faust. Static analysis is used to extract information from the source code of a program or a binary without executing the program. It can be used to identify properties, such as correctness, to optimize, or predict the performance of programs [9].

In the case of general purpose languages such as C, data flow frequency analysis [30] has been used to predict the number of times instructions are executed. When combined with cache analysis techniques [31], this strategy could estimate hardware dependent performance of program without executing this program on the target hardware. Unfortunately, the complexity of hardware and the expressiveness of general purpose languages can often lead to situations where no pertinent estimation can be made due to cache effects and undecidable program properties.

Figure 8: Signal expression of *Echo*. The actors in grey denote that they produce the value that determines the delay of *Echo* in samples.

Figure 9: Subset of SDF generated from signal expression of *Echo*. The actors are labelled with their IDs in parenthesis. The edge between (1) and (4) denotes an N sample delay, which is set by the user.

In the context of DSP applications, however, where applications tend to be more regular and less dynamic, static analysis becomes much more efficient. This is especially true when programs are defined using domain specific languages such as Faust. For example, the StreamIt language [32] and the SigmaC language [33] were used to express programs as SDF. From this intermediate representation, the compiler toolchain can generate binary code optimized for many-core hardware. In this context, static analysis is used to determine memory requirements of applications for given performance constraints or to predict performance of a particular task-to-core mapping of the application.

There are two main use cases where dataflow modeling could be used for performance analysis. First, similarly to StreamIt [32] or SigmaC [33], the application’s behaviour can be faithfully expressed using dataflow models. For example, in the context of DSP hardware design, a fine-grain and functionally equivalent representation of a program is produced [34, 35, 21]. In this case, dataflow can be used to verify correctness, analyse the performance of a program, and even generate optimised code for a particular hardware target such as FPGA [34, 21] or GPU [35]. When the programming language does not exactly match dataflow models, static analysis can still be used to estimate performance and to support the compilers making decisions. This is for example what is done by the MAPS [36] framework, that describes applications using the C for process networks (CPN) language, and guides task-to-core

mapping decision using trace-based analysis tools.

Similarly to task-to-core mapping problems, our objective is to use SDF models to help the user make decisions in choosing the right hardware, by predicting the performance for specific targets such as FPGA devices (e.g. Syfala [37]).

7. CONCLUSION

In this work, we introduce a methodology to model Faust application as SDFs, forming the foundation for a longer term project. In the future, we plan to use this transformation to enable the use of static analysis technique for SDFs in order to predict performance metrics such as throughput and delay. As a motivational example, we present performance estimates for the *Echo* application, by considering what could be a potential FPGA implementation.

Modelling Faust programs as SDFs, and the associated performance analysis methods could also support the code generation process. The SDF model can act as an Intermediate Representation wherein the performance of the implementation can be evaluated and optimized prior to code generation.

Beyond the use of dataflow models to predict performance or event generate programs, an additional use case could be to provide feedback on the implementation of the Faust program, directly to the user. For example, it might be possible to provide real-time feedback to users while they are writing Faust programs in an IDE by periodically compiling and modelling their program as an SDF.

Moving forward, we advocate for integrating more high-level analysis in the programming workflow so that the user can have a comprehensive diagnosis of which parts of their program could be a performance bottleneck.

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Figure 10: Self-timed schedule of *Echo* with delay of 3 samples. Initial firings are coloured *orange*, while periodic firings are coloured *blue*. The column labels represent time units while the row labels indicate the ID of the actor (as listed in Figure 9 that the firing corresponds to).

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